

Semi-Quantitative Fractionation of Attapulgite and Illite from their Natural Mixture

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A natural clay from Mudh, Rajasthan was fractionated by centrifuging it with alcohol-bromoform mixtures of various densities. The fractions collected successively at specific gravities, 2.05, 2.15 and >2.15 were identified by DTA; they were concentrates of attapulgite, illite and calcite weighing 14, 82 and 4 percent respectively.

BASED on the apparent specific gravity assumed by clay minerals in polar liquids, Loughnan¹ reported isolation of montmorillonite from halloysite using a bromoform-alcohol mixture. Later Jelacic and Thalce² used the same technique for estimation of montmorillonite in bentonitic clays. The separation is affected by the behaviour of montmorillonite which swells on adsorption of polar liquids between the silicate sheets and is floated clear of the contaminating minerals. The analogy could possibly be extended to the isolation of attapulgite whose open structure permits permeation of polar liquids through all sides into the channels of fixed dimensions positioned between the brucite layers of the mineral, this would result in a decrease in its apparent specific gravity and cause separation from the non-swelling type of clays. The present paper deals with the application of this phenomena to fractionation of a natural clay mixture of attapulgite and illite from Mudh³, (72°5':27°52') Rajasthan.

Experimental

The clay was thoroughly dispersed in sodium hexametaphosphate solution (conc. 0.1%), filtered and dried at 110°. It was then ground and sifted to a particle size, -170+200 mesh, BSS. About 0.2 g of the electrolyte-treated and sized material was centrifuged with a 10 ml solution of bromoform and ethyl alcohol. Fractions were collected successively at specific gravities, 2.05 (Fraction I) and 2.15 (Fraction II), washed with alcohol to remove bromoform, dried at 100° and weighed. Fraction heavier than sp.gr. 2.15 (Fraction III) was collected separately and weighed. The weight fractions determined were: Fraction I, 0.14; Fraction II, 0.82; and Fraction III, 0.04. Apparent specific gravities of pure samples of attapulgite and illite were determined prior to subjecting the natural clay mixture to fractionation in the media of alcohol and bromoform. The results are set out as: attapulgite (Georgia, USA), 2.00; illite (Fithian, USA), 2.20.

Fractions I and II and the composite sample were analysed on the Leeds and Northrup DTA apparatus which consists of an automatic X-Y recorder, a programme controller and a furnace with a heating rate of 12.5°/min. The sample holder was of Roberts-Grimshaw pattern embedded with Pt-Pt 10%Rh thermocouples. Calcined alumina was used as the inert reference material. The weight of the sample was, 0.4 g in each case.

Results and Discussion

The DTA curve of the composite sample (curve A, Fig. 1) shows endothermic peaks at 100°, 535° and 850° followed by an exothermic reaction with its maximum at about 905°. The curve is indicative of an illite. There also appears a small endothermic

Fig. 1. DTA records of Mudh earth: A—Composite sample, B—Fraction I, separated at apparent specific gravity 1.95-2.05; C—Fraction II, separated at apparent sp. gr. 2.05-2.15.

effect in the range, 210°/310° which is characteristic of all magnesium bearing clays, and which is inferred to the removal of water co-ordinated with magnesium. This latter effect and the dehydroxylation reaction at 535° are suggestive of the presence of attapulgite. The large endothermic peak appearing at 780° is mainly due to calcite associated with the clay.

The DTA records of Fractions I and II (curves B and C, Fig. 1) separated at apparent sp. gr., 2.05 and between 2.05 and 2.15 respectively seem to differ in their main characteristics which indicate the mineral separation as it is held in the following. The DTA curve of Fraction I shows more pronounced endothermic effect in the temperature range, 170°/280° due to dehydration of Mg-bonded water which at the same time indicates the enrichment of attapulgite in the fraction. Besides, the initial dehydration reaction peak of Fraction I is relatively more intense and the main dehydroxylation reaction maximum occurs at a slightly lower temperature than that of the composite sample which corroborate to the above conclusion. The DTA curve of Fraction II is marked by a less pronounced effect on dehydration and broadening of the base which are diagnostic features

of most illites. Also, the endothermic peak around 225° which appears in the DTA records of the composite sample as well as in Fraction I (curves A and B, Fig. 1) and which indicates the presence of attapulgite is almost flattened in the DTA profile of Fraction II (curve C, Fig. 1). The characterisation obviously indicates the fractionation of attapulgite and illite in the sample. Further, the intense endothermic peak at 780° appearing in the DTA record of the composite sample is totally absent from the DTA records of Fractions I and II; this indicates a complete separation of calcite from these fractions.

The investigations have established the phenomena of partial fractionation of attapulgite and illite at their selective densities in polar media, also a complete separation of calcite from the clay fractions and hence, the usefulness of the technique in the study of complex clay mixtures.

References

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